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Everyday Life in Wartime Ukraine in the Perspective of Feminist Political Economy

When war occurs, its repercussions are felt far beyond the front lines. They permeate the private sphere, intersecting with other forms of violence and deeply affecting the everyday reality of individuals, regardless of their proximity to the conflict.

Narratives of «everyday war» and «everyday peace» attempt to capture the complex relationship between violence and the rhythm of daily life. Many of these narratives build upon a feminist understanding of violence as existing along a continuum. However, few offer an in-depth examination of how practices of social reproduction specifically intersect with patterns of violence in the reconfiguration of the everyday during wartime. We define social reproduction as the socially necessary work central to the production of life itself. This encompasses biological reproduction, physical and emotional care for one's family and community, as well as the labor that enables the promotion of the cultural and spiritual heritage of a community.

We have found the concept of «the everyday» particularly useful in framing our thinking about the ways in which social reproduction occurs in war and post-war contexts and in imagining feminist alternatives to dominant neoliberal post-war reconstruction models. Peace literature has rarely applied the lens of social reproduction when discussing everyday peace. When everyday practices of peace are addressed, they are typically interpreted either through the lens of localized people-to-people dialogue and trust-building or through the prism of the ethics of care — a way of thinking and acting that can be more conducive to building a peaceful society. We argue that taking everyday practices of social reproduction seriously, as part of the strategy used to survive and recover from conflict, provides a deeper understanding of how violence operates in a society and points toward new ways of rebuilding after it.

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The everyday, as a social construction distinct from simple day-to-day activity, emerges as a site where violence is reproduced. In this context, the structural violence of the capitalist system becomes intertwined with the violence of war. In Ukraine, new challenges in practicing social reproduction during the conflict have contributed to the entrenchment of patriarchal norms and orders. This reproduces structural violence against women, who increasingly find themselves confined to the home and burdened with domestic labor, while social reproduction infrastructure continues to shrink due to wartime destruction. On the other hand, the everyday is co-constructed by a wide range of actors, including both those in power and those who may appear powerless. It is a social fabric co-created by people and institutions, elites and non-elites, forming routines and responding to recurrent needs. There are many ways in which the everyday can become a site of resistance and contestation, where agents can enact daily life in ways that counter or confront mainstream rhythms and systems. Peacebuilding scholars have highlighted the potential of the everyday as a significant site for change and resistance.

Feminist scholars have argued that providing care through community self-organized legal aid, childcare, healthcare, and psychological counseling can foster trust and ultimately undermine patterns of violence. However, most accounts of care practices in peacebuilding center disproportionately on care as an ethic rather than the labor of care central to social reproduction. Understanding violence, survival, and peacebuilding through the lens of social reproductive labor adds greater nuance and depth to what everyday peace or indeed everyday recovery might look like.

Finally, the conceptualization of the everyday as a site of survival is at the heart of our exploration. Much of survival is enabled through social reproduction. We view survival not as a single act, but rather as an outcome of practices, including everyday acts of care and social reproduction. Tracing the patterns of survival and the practices that lead to it can provide important insights into how violence interacts with and reshapes the everyday. While social reproductive labor is always necessary for the survival of individuals, communities, and societies — evident in caring for children, the elderly, and the sick, feeding families, and cultivating cultural heritage — its salience becomes particularly visible when violence renders these everyday practices less routine. For example, securing food or medicine may require standing in long lines or traveling great distances, and preserving familial ties might demand crossing checkpoints and putting oneself in danger. Furthermore, the routine of care and social reproduction is frequently disturbed by airstrikes and the necessity of spending prolonged periods in bomb shelters.

When this occurs, the everyday becomes fundamentally reshaped by violence, and social reproduction becomes the avenue through which this reshaping takes place. There is much to gain in viewing peace through the prism of social reproduction, as it allows us to see how violence operates through the interplay between violence, survival, and resistance. Social reproduction exists in a space of liminality, being simultaneously entrenched in dangerous violence and acting as a means of resisting it.

Applying a social reproduction lens to better understand and disentangle both the everyday workings of violence and the everyday resistance to them is an important strategy that has been underutilized in the literature on conflict and peace. This paper represents part of our theoretical work carried out within the framework of the project «Caring to Survive, Surviving to Care: Gendered Practices of Survival, Social Reproduction, and Circles of Violence in Ukraine». This initiative is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation under the Solution-oriented Research for Development program. It is implemented by an international team involving specialists from the Gender Centre of the Geneva Graduate Institute, the Women's International League for Peace and Freedom, the Center for Social and Labor Research in Ukraine, and V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University. Our project aims to contribute to a more feminist-oriented post-war reconstruction in Ukraine by bringing to light the role of social reproduction and everyday survival practices in responding to and healing from violence.